

POLICY BRIEF

Reducing Ageism in the Second Half of Life

Policy Brief No. 1

May 2026

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Reducing Ageism in the Second Half of Life

An approach to addressing self- and other-directed ageism among older adults

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Executive Summary

Population ageing is one of the defining demographic trends of the 21st century. As societies age, promoting healthy, active and inclusive ageing has become an international policy priority. However, these efforts are undermined by persistent age-based stereotypes, prejudice and discrimination — **ageism**. Ageism refers to **stereotypes** (how we think), **prejudice** (how we feel) and **discrimination** (how we act) towards others or oneself based on age (WHO, 2021).

Addressing ageism in later life is essential for improving health outcomes, strengthening social participation and ensuring sustainable ageing societies. Public debate has focused on discrimination against older adults from younger groups or institutions. Yet ageism also operates *within* older populations themselves (Levy, 2009). These dynamics are understudied and insufficiently addressed in policies and interventions (Ayalon, 2025).

This policy brief introduces **HalfLife**: a research initiative to understand and reduce ageism among adults aged 60+, introducing new primary research from the Czech Republic, Germany, Israel and the United Kingdom. HALFLIFE (a five-year project funded by the European Research Council, ERC-2024-AdV, grant ID 101198899) will produce tangible evidence and actionable recommendations for policymakers and international organizations across Europe.

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Key Messages

01

Ageism operates both externally and internally

Older adults experience ageism but can also internalize and reproduce ageist beliefs about themselves and others.

02

Consequences are wide-ranging

Ageism affects health, participation in society, productivity, and well-being.

03

Interventions targeting ageism among older adults are scarce

Existing policies primarily focus on protecting older people from discrimination rather than addressing ageist beliefs and practices within older populations.

04

Evidence-based solutions are urgently needed

Research and policy must develop and test interventions that address both self-directed and other-directed ageism among older adults.

Ageism in Ageing Societies

Population ageing is transforming societies across Europe and around the world. Increasing longevity and declining fertility mean that the proportion of older adults is growing steadily, reshaping labour markets, healthcare systems and social policies.

In this context, how societies perceive and treat ageing becomes critically important. **Ageism** refers to stereotypes (“how we think”), prejudice (“how we feel”) and discrimination (“how we act”) towards others or oneself based on age (WHO, 2021). Ageism can occur at multiple levels:

- Individual: through personal beliefs and behaviours.
- Societal: through cultural narratives about ageing and older people.
- Institutional: through policies and practices that disadvantage certain age groups.

International policy frameworks increasingly recognize the harmful impact of ageism. Organizations such as the AGE Platform Europe (and its *EU Action Plan to Combat Ageism*), the World Health Organization and the United Nations highlight ageism as a major challenge within the *UN Decade of Healthy Ageing* (2021–2030).

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Moving Beyond a One-Sided View of Ageism

Despite growing recognition of ageism, the popular narrative continues to frame older people primarily as targets of ageism. Yet older adults are not only victims of ageism but *agents* of ageism, shaping and reproducing dominant, negative perceptions of ageing. Recognizing this dual role is an essential step towards developing effective strategies to reduce ageism.

1. Self-Directed Ageism

Self-directed ageism occurs when older adults internalize age-related stereotypes, absorb negative feelings about ageing, and translate these into their own behaviours and decisions (Ayalon & Tesch-Römer, 2017). After a lifetime of exposure to deeply ingrained cultural narratives associating ageing with decline, dependence and reduced capability, individuals can begin to frame themselves through this lens (Levy, 2009). This can influence self-belief about their own capabilities, emotional responses to ageing (e.g. fear, resignation or reduced self-confidence), and behaviour and decision-making — such as withdrawing from activities, limiting social engagement, or reduced engagement with the labour market.

2. Other-Directed Ageism

Ageism is also expressed in how older adults perceive and interact with other older people (Dobbs et al., 2008). Stereotypes about who is “active,” “capable,” or “frail” can shape judgments and social comparisons, while underlying attitudes can incite subtle forms of distancing or devaluation. These perceptions can translate into everyday behaviours — such as exclusion, avoidance or differential treatment — that reinforce and reproduce broader patterns of ageism.

Why This Matters

Self-directed and other-directed ageism are interconnected. The way individuals think and feel about their own ageing can influence how they treat others, while everyday interactions can reinforce broader beliefs about ageing as decline or limitation. Together, these processes act iteratively, sustaining age-related stereotypes, emotions and behaviours over time.

Interventions addressing these forms of ageism are rare and under-researched. Most existing initiatives focus on intergenerational contact or on reducing ageist attitudes among younger people via educational initiatives. Moreover, there is a sustained lack of coherent and comprehensive evaluation of anti-ageism initiatives, preventing shared learning and progress.

KEY INSIGHT

Reducing ageism requires addressing both internalized beliefs about ageing and ageist attitudes expressed within older populations as well as towards older people.

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What Can Be Done: Developing HALFLIFE Interventions

Over the next five years, **HalfLife** will develop and test a suite of interventions that are indicative of a reduction in ageism. The final product will be a programme of **three interventions** that are proven to reduce ageism among older people and can be easily implemented.

If ageism is sustained through interconnected patterns of stereotypes, prejudice and discrimination, then effective responses must target all three dimensions. HALFLIFE addresses this gap by developing a new generation of interventions that explicitly recognize older adults as agents as well as targets of ageism.

A key feature of this approach is the **involvement of older adults in the intervention design process**. This ensures that interventions reflect lived experiences, are meaningful to participants, and are sensitive to the diversity of later life.

Currently in the design phase, HalfLife is working with older adults to design interventions that:

- support individuals in reflecting on and reshaping how they think about ageing, how they feel about it, and how these perceptions translate into behaviour
- create opportunities to reconsider assumptions about capability, participation and social roles in later life
- foster forms of interaction that reduce age-based distinctions and strengthen mutual recognition among older adults
- support the fulfillment of older persons' potential

KEY MESSAGE

Reducing ageism requires interventions that address stereotypes, prejudice and discrimination together — by engaging older adults as active agents of change in how ageing is thought, felt and enacted.

An International Approach

A central question for policymakers is whether anti-ageism interventions can work across different societies. Ageism is shaped by social norms, institutional arrangements and cultural expectations about ageing. In practice, this means that the social reality of ageism differs between countries.

HALFLIFE implements and evaluates its interventions in four countries, representing contrasting patterns of ageism:

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Czech Republic	Increasing perceived discrimination in later life
Germany	A U-shaped pattern, affecting both younger and older groups
United Kingdom	Higher perceived discrimination among younger individuals, declining with age
Israel	A U-shaped pattern, affecting both younger and older groups

This comparative design will explicitly identify interventions that are robust, transferable and scalable across diverse contexts. Recognising that interventions cannot simply be transplanted unchanged from one context to another, HALFLIFE interventions will be adapted to each national context, ensuring that they are relevant, acceptable and accessible for participants. In this way, the project balances two key objectives: identifying interventions that are generalizable in their impact, while preserving a context-sensitive design and implementation.

Policy Implications

For policymakers and practitioners, ageism presents a critical challenge. Many policies aim to support health, participation and inclusion in ageing societies (Walker & Maltby, 2012). However, their effectiveness depends not only on institutional provision, but also on whether individuals perceive opportunities as relevant, accessible or appropriate. When internalized and interpersonal forms of ageism shape how people think, feel and act, even well-designed policies may not reach their full potential.

Addressing ageism in later life requires coordinated action across research, policy and practice. Several priorities emerge:

- Develop and evaluate targeted interventions that address ageism both within and towards older populations.
- Support internationally comparable research to identify scalable solutions adaptable across policy contexts.
- Engage older adults as active participants in designing and implementing anti-ageism programmes.
- Move beyond awareness-raising toward evidence-based approaches that demonstrably influence how ageism operates in practice.

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Conclusion: Rethinking Ageism in Ageing Societies

As populations age, policymakers are increasingly confronted with a central question: *how can societies ensure that longer lives translate into healthier, more engaged and more inclusive communities?* Addressing ageism is an essential part of that answer.

Ageism is often treated primarily as a problem of discrimination directed towards older people by younger generations. Yet the evidence increasingly suggests that this perspective is only partial. Age-related stereotypes, prejudice and discrimination do not disappear when individuals grow older; they develop across the life course and shape how older adults view themselves and others in later life.

HalfLife will contribute to this shift in perspective by examining ageism among older adults and testing interventions across the Czech Republic, Germany, Israel and the UK. The next HALFLIFE policy brief will describe and evaluate these interventions in greater detail.

For policymakers, the broader implication is clear. Addressing ageism cannot rely solely on combating discrimination or promoting positive images of ageing at a societal level. It must also consider how individuals themselves interpret and negotiate the meaning of ageing. Policies that engage older adults as active participants in reshaping these processes have the potential to strengthen health, participation and social cohesion in ageing societies.

Ultimately, reducing ageism is about ensuring that the longer lives made possible by social and medical progress become a resource for individuals and societies alike.

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